

**e-Service Learning for more digital
and inclusive EU Higher Education
systems**

**Manual
on methodologies and procedures for
the e-SL training course**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Content :

INTRODUCTION 3

STRUCTURE OF THE COURSE 4

LOGIN INTO THE E-LEARNING PLATFORM MOD (BASED ON MOODLE)..... 8

Introduction

The **Manual on methodologies and procedures for the e-SL training course** was created to support the open e-course within the project “eSL4EU: e-Service Learning for more digital and inclusive EU Higher Education systems”, and is intended for higher education teachers who plan to integrate e-Service Learning (e-SL) and help their colleagues to implement e-SL in their teaching.

The project and the e-course focus on emergence of e-Service Learning as an innovative pedagogical approach based on experiential learning (Salam et al., 2019) within the context of higher education in Europe. e-SL is a course-based, credit-bearing educational experience in which students participate in an organized service activity that meets identified community needs, and they reflect on the service activity to gain further understanding of course content, a broader appreciation of the academic discipline, and enhanced sense of civic responsibility. In e-SL the educational experience is mediated by Information and Communication Technology (ICT) wherein the instructional component, the service component or both are conducted online, often in a hybrid model. As such, e-Service Learning provides many opportunities in online education, because it offers an experiential praxis in which students are involved through technology in civic enquiry, in reflections and actions, collaborating with the community.

The set of guidelines and tools has been developed addressing higher education teachers aiming at the following objectives: 1) To build learning systems with an innovative pedagogical approach that integrates community services into the students' curriculum; 2) To promote a change in the traditional assistive model (service for the community) to a horizontal model of solidarity (service with the community); 3) To spread the knowledge on e-SL methodologies developing training materials for academics to adopt e-SL in their teaching practices, guiding their students in implementing e-Service-Learning and assessing their learning while addressing social needs of people with fewer opportunities, especially in cases of emergencies such as the pandemic or other disruptive events and 4) To develop HE lecturers/trainers/students' digital skills aimed at the implementation of e-SL methodologies.

Guidelines, framework and ideas for implement e-SL in the academic teaching can be found in the e-learning course in English *e-Service-Learning for more digital and inclusive EU Higher Education systems* **available on the following link:** <https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=482>

The course is also available in Croatian (<https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=487>), Italian (<https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=542>), Polish (<https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=538>), Slovak (<https://lms-ext.umb.sk/course/view.php?id=158>) and Romanian (<https://traininghub.reu.pub.ro/course/index.php?categoryid=1>).

Structure of the course

The e-course *e-Service-Learning for more digital and inclusive EU Higher Education systems* is developed by the e-SL4EU consortium (<https://e-sl4eu.us.edu.pl/>) of 6 partners from 5 EU countries: Poland, Italy, Croatia, Romania and Slovakia.

Participants in this course (academic teachers) will learn key characteristics of e-Service-Learning (e-SL) and will be provided with training tools for the adoption of e-SL to build inclusive higher education systems.

By the end of this e-course, you will be able to:

- identify design principles and quality elements of e-SL projects for building up an online or blended training course,
- use instructional design principles and strategies that best fit different interactive activities and instructional goals
- select the e-SL course design that is relevant to your teaching practice, guiding your students in implementing e-Service-Learning and assessing their learning while addressing social needs of people with fewer opportunities,
- create engaging, effective and inclusive e-SL course to involve your students in e-SL projects.

Before you dive into e-Service Learning, take the initial **self-assessment test** that will help you remember what service-learning (SL) is about and how to deliver a SL course.

In **Units 1 - 4** you can learn about the theory of e-SL and instructional design. **Unit 5** brings instructional design options for your e-SL courses and **Unit 6** provides examples of good practices from diverse study fields and different EU countries.

In **Unit 7** academic teachers will learn how to design their own e-SL course.

Final self-assessment tool has been designed for you to self-assess your motivation and skills for developing and supervising e-Service Learning projects.

Finally, all participants in this course will receive the **Course completion certificate**.

This Certificate can only be issued after the anonymous Course feedback has been completed.

UNIT1

Unit 1 on **e-SL Design Framework** aims to provide a comprehensive tool that could help teachers, university leaders, community partners, and other stakeholders to design effective and meaningful e-SL activities. The framework considers the multiple

factors influencing learning and student achievement in e-SL activities. The framework incorporates **three pillars of the 'new culture of learning' - places, people, and partnerships** (Thomas & Brown, 2012) – that translate an ecosystemic approach to learning in higher education. The three pillars interconnect four clusters of design principles with the intention of promoting student engagement.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- recognize the different components of the e-SL Design Framework and how they interact;
- identify the multiple factors influencing learning and student achievement in e-SL activities;
- apply the e-SL Design Framework in specific contexts;
- analyze and evaluate how the e-SL Design Framework translates into an ecosystemic approach to learning in HE.

UNIT2

Unit 2 on **e-SL Design Principles** presents a set of statements that put a clear focus on a specific mindset or the requirements which should guide the design activity of teachers, university leaders, community partners, and other stakeholders. Unit 2 provides the list and definitions of the e-SL design principles with a short explanation. In the exercises we will use the short descriptions of three case studies and you should recognize which e-SL Design Principles were omitted in the design. In the end, you will describe how you can implement Design Principles in your e-SL course. The act of examining new information and experiences in your own words will help you better understand, develop, and strengthen your knowledge of the Design Principles.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- understand the essential e-SL Design Principles
- explain the importance of the e-SL Design Principles
- assess / evaluate the importance of particular groups of principles in designing (clusters) of e-service-learning course
- creatively incorporate e-SL Design Principles into own e-SL course.

UNIT3

Unit 3 provides the definition of the e-SL quality elements and the list of the e-SL quality elements with the short explanation. In the exercise we will use the short good and bad examples from practice and participants should choose the e-SL quality element which was or was not part of the example. In the last section of the lesson participants should choose 5 elements and describe how they will implement them in their own e-SL course.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- explain the e-SL quality elements,
- creatively adapt e-SL quality elements in different situations.
- implement e-SL quality elements in planning your own course.

UNIT4

The aim of this unit is to teach you how to use instructional design principles and strategies that best fit different interactive activities and instructional goals.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- apply principles of Cognitive theory of multimedia learning in design of learning materials
- identify the principles, structure and elements of digital storytelling for academic knowledge to be integrated into a real situation
- use scenarios to provide learners with a realistic context where they can make choices
- implement toolkit lessons and microlearning to increase learner engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention
- create games to harness human gameplay for tackling community issues

UNIT5

This unit presents you with the **instructional design** of the **four e-service-learning courses from the four EU countries: Italy, Slovakia, Romania and Croatia**. For each course, you can analyze the level of study program, ECTS value, general framework, teaching methods, learning outcomes and the detailed description of the instructional design.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- analyze the characteristics of existing e-SL courses;
- incorporate the design elements of existing e-SL courses in your own learning activities.

UNIT6

This unit presents best e-service-learning practices from the four EU countries: Italy, Slovakia, Romania and Croatia.

UNIT7

This unit allows you to **document your e-service-learning project ideas**, as well as learning needs and community needs you aim to satisfy in a structured way.

Upon completion of this unit you will be able to:

- design and plan your e-SL project / course based on what you learned in the previous modules
- document the process and ideas for developing your e-SL project / course

Login into the e-learning platform MoD (based on Moodle)

You can access the Moodle system at the web address mod.srce.hr.

(To change the language of the interface, you need to select the drop-down menu with list of languages on the menu bar.)

Caption 1: E-learning platform MoD

You can login to the e-learning platform with the AAI@EduHr electronic identity (only for participants from Croatia) or with a **local user account**.

Caption 2: Log in using local user account button

Users who log in to the Mod for the first time using a local account should create it first. To create a local user account, select the **Log in using local user account** button and then the **Create new account** button in the **Is this your first time here?** block.

Is this your first time here?

You must complete the following steps in order to gain access to e-courses:

1. Fill out the [New Account](#) web form with your personal details.
- 2 After submitting the form, you should receive an email at the email address you provided.

3. Please carefully read the email and click on the link in order to confirm your registration and log in to the system.

Check out our [quick guide](#) on logging into the MoD system.

Create new account

Caption 3: Create new account button

The next step is to select the desired username and password and enter additional user information. After the user completes and submits the form, he/she receives a notification to his/her e-mail address about the created local user account, in which he/she must select a link to confirm the user account creation.

New account
Username

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, or #

Password

Email address

Email (again)

First name

Surname

City/town

Country
Croatia

Personal data that need to be submitted are collected solely for the purpose of enabling the use of particular service and record keeping and will not be disclosed to third parties.
Before starting the registration procedure, I hereby confirm that I am informed of the purpose of collecting and processing the requested personal data and I hereby give my consent to Srce to collect and process this data in accordance with the provisions of GDPR (REGULATION (EU) 2016/679) and the Act on the Implementation of General Data Protection Regulation (OG 42/18).

Create my new account

There are required fields in this form marked

Caption 4: Local account creation form

At each subsequent login to the system, the user logs in with his/her data in the **Local user log in** block.

Log in to MoD - virtualno okruženje za projekte e-učenja u zajednici

Username or email

Password

Log in

[Lost password?](#)

Is this your first time here?

You must complete the following steps in order to gain access to e-courses:

1. Fill out the [New Account](#) web form with your personal details.
2. After submitting the form, you should receive an email at the email address you provided.
3. Please carefully read the email and click on the link in order to confirm your registration and log in to the system.

Check out our [quick guide](#) on logging into the MoD system.

[Create new account](#)

Some courses may allow guest access

[Log in as a guest](#)

[English \(en\)](#) * [Cookies notice](#)

Caption 5: Local user log in page

After successfully logging in to the MoD, the user has access to his/her own homepage and enrolled e-courses (see image below).

Caption 6: Welcome screen of the MoD system

Now, copy the following link <https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=482> at the address bar of your browser to access the course in English language (**e-Service-Learning for more digital and inclusive EU Higher Education systems**).

Caption 7: Address bar with the link: <https://mod.srce.hr/course/view.php?id=482>

In the next step, click on the **Enrol me in this course** to access the course.

Caption 8: Click on the **Enrol me in this course**

In case of password problems or incorrect data, users can request the creation of a new password using the **Forgotten your username or password** link or contact moodle@srce.hr for help. In case of technical problems, please do not hesitate to contact **University Computing Center- SRCE** at e-mail: helpdesk@srce.hr